

Some Newer Quinazolones as Psychotropic Agents

ISHTIAQ AHMAD*

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

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Some substituted-quinazolones have been synthesised with a view to evaluate CNS activity. The psychopharmacological screening has shown to possess anticonvulsant activity, observed against penlylenetetrazole. *In vivo* MAO inhibitory effect of these compounds were studied during oxidative deamination of benzylamine using rat brain homogenate.

MONOAMINE oxidase (MAO) enzyme has been considered to play an important role in the activity of central nervous system (CNS)¹. This could possibly account for anticonvulsant properties of MAO inhibitors which has been shown to be closely associated with the elevation of 5-hydroxytryptamine and noradrenaline. Diverse biological activities² prompted us to synthesise a large number of quinazolones having phenoxy and thioureido moiety at position 2 and 3 respectively with a view to evaluate their potential psychotropic activity.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Structures of the

compounds were checked by ir and nmr spectroscopy and elemental analyses.

Synthesis of anthranils: The compounds were synthesised according to the method reported in literature³.

2-Phenoxymethyl-3-(p-nitrophenyl)-4(3H)-quinazolones (2): The quinazolones were prepared by the method of Kishore⁴. Equimolar quantity of anthranils and p-nitroaniline were heated. On cooling a jelly like mass separated out, which was crystallised from appropriate solvent to obtain the corresponding quinazolone (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE QUINAZOLONES (2)*

Compd. no.	X	X ₁	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
2a	H	H	H	203–04	57	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂
2b	Br	H	H	236–38	42	C ₁₇ H ₉ BrN ₃ O ₂
2c	Br	Br	H	281	51	C ₁₇ H ₇ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂
2d	I	H	H	195–96	54	C ₁₇ H ₉ IN ₃ O ₂
2e	H	H	Me	117–18	37	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂
2f	Br	H	Me	212–18	40	C ₁₈ H ₉ BrN ₃ O ₂
2g	Br	Br	Me	179	35	C ₁₈ H ₇ Br ₂ N ₃ O ₂
2h	I	H	Me	189–91	42	C ₁₈ H ₉ IN ₃ O ₂

*O analysis found satisfactory.

2-Phenoxymethyl-3-(p-aminophenyl)-4(3H)-quinazolones (3): The compounds were prepared according to the method of Richard *et al.*⁵. Hydrazine hydrate (2 ml, 0.04 mol; 99–100%) was added dropwise to a solution of 2 (0.005 mol) in hot absolute ethanol. Freshly prepared Raney nickel catalyst was added slowly. The reaction was allowed to proceed, until all the hydrazine hydrate decomposed. The catalyst was filtered off and the filtrate was immediately evaporated to dryness. The resulting solid mass was crystallised from ethanol are given in Table 2.

2-Phenoxymethyl-3-(4-N¹-substituted-phenylthioureido)phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolone (4): The compounds were synthesised according to the method by George *et al.*⁶. Phenylisothiocyanate (0.01 mol) was added to a solution of 3 (0.01 mol) in benzene and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was removed and the resulting solid mass was crystallised from ethanol (Table 3).

*Present address: Department of Chemistry, Shia Degree College, Daliganj, Lucknow-226 007.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF THE QUINAZOLONES (3)*

Compd. no.	X	X ₁	R	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
3a	H	H	H	113-14	42	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄
3b	Br	H	H	105-06	47	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ BrN ₂ O ₄
3c	Br	Br	H	98	51	C ₁₁ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄
3d	I	H	H	118-19	46	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ IN ₂ O ₄
3e	H	H	Me	107	31	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄
3f	Br	H	Me	117-18	49	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ BrN ₂ O ₄
3g	Br	Br	Me	130	40	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄
3h	I	H	Me	103-05	57	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ IN ₂ O ₄

*C analy is found satisfactory.

(w/v). The reaction mixture consisted of phosphate buffer (pH=7.5; 0.5 M, 0.5 ml), benzylamine hydrochloride (0.1 M, 0.1 ml) and brain homogenate (equivalent to 20 mg wet tissue weight, 2 ml). The compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol (100%) and used at a final concentration of 1 × 10⁻³ M. The compounds were incubated for 40 min at 37° followed by the addition of substrate. The enzymatic reaction was stopped by the addition of 10% HClO₄ (1 ml) and the precipitated protein was removed by centrifugation. The absorbance of aliquot was

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL DATA OF THE QUINAZOLONES (4)*

Compd. no.	X	X ₁	R	R ₁	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Approximate LD ₅₀	Anti-convulsant activity Protection (%)	Mortality (%)	MAO inhibition (%) Mean + SMA
4a	H	H	H	Cl	178	53	C ₁₀ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	600	50	50	35.8 ± 0.3161
4b	Br	H	H	Cl	195-96	33	C ₁₀ H ₈ BrClN ₂ O ₄ S	765	50	30	32.2 ± 0.2176
4c	Br	Br	H	Cl	280	57	C ₁₀ H ₇ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	681	70	30	25.6 ± 0.3412
4d	H	H	H	Br	203-05	48	C ₁₀ H ₉ BrN ₂ O ₄ S	1000	50	40	40.8 ± 0.3101
4e	H	H	H	Me	106-08	55	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ S	681	20	80	70.8 ± 0.4211
4f	Br	Br	Me	Me	169	43	C ₁₁ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	1000	30	70	62.2 ± 0.1718
4g	I	H	Me	Me	203-10	61	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ IN ₂ O ₄ S	1000	40	50	62.2 ± 0.5178
4h	H	H	Me	Br	202-04	31	C ₁₁ H ₉ BrN ₂ O ₄ S	600	30	60	60.0 ± 0.4121
4i	H	H	Me	Cl	235-37	45	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	681	50	50	58.2 ± 0.4128
4j	Br	H	Me	Cl	265-57	33	C ₁₁ H ₈ BrClN ₂ O ₄ S	1000	40	60	60.1 ± 0.2171
4k	Br	Br	Me	Cl	265	43	C ₁₁ H ₇ Br ₂ ClN ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—
4l	I	H	Me	Cl	217-18	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ IN ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—
4m	H	H	Me	Br	202-04	31	C ₁₁ H ₉ BrN ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—
4n	I	H	H	Br	368	61	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ BrIN ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—
4o	Br	Br	H	Br	117-18	47	C ₁₀ H ₈ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—
4p	Br	H	H	Br	279	34	C ₁₀ H ₈ BrN ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—
4q	I	H	H	Cl	187-88	38	C ₁₀ H ₉ IN ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—
4r	I	H	H	Me	216-17	38	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ IN ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—
4s	Br	H	H	Me	170-79	40	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ BrN ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—
4t	Br	Br	H	Me	210	35	C ₁₁ H ₉ Br ₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	—	—	—	—

*C and H analyses found satisfactory.

Biological activity :

Toxicity : Acute toxicity study was performed with administered i.p. 60 albino mice of either sex in different doses and approximate LD₅₀ values were determined by the conventional procedure⁷.

Anticonvulsant activity : Anticonvulsant activity was determined according to the reported method in literature⁸.

Monoamine oxidase activity : The spectrophotometric method was used for the determination of MAO activity of rat brain homogenate using benzylamine as a substrate⁹. The benzaldehyde formed during oxidative deamination of benzylamine was estimated by using a Hitachi-Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer at 250 nm.

Male adult rats (150-200 g) were killed by decapitation. The brain was quickly removed and homogenised in ice-cold sucrose solution (0.25 M) with the help of a Potter-Elvehjem homogeniser. The homogenate was diluted with sucrose (0.25 M) and the final concentration was adjusted to 10%

measured at 250 nm and the percent inhibition was calculated.

Results and Discussion

The approximate LD₅₀ values of this series ranged from 600 to 1000 mg/kg and above showing their relative non-toxicity. Maximum values were shown by compound 4d, 4f, 4g and 4j (Table 3).

Anticonvulsant values were reflected in the range 20-70% (Table 3). The substituent chloro group at position R₁ and bromo group at position 6 and 8 of quinazolone moiety exhibited maximum degree of protection (70%) against pentylenetetrazole-induced seizures, while methyl group at position R and R₁ revealed low activity. In general, electrophilic substituents at position R₁ exhibited greater degree of activity, and nucleophilic substituents at position R and R₁ revealed low activity. Data on anticonvulsant activity and 24 hour pentylenetetrazole mortality indicated some association between increased protection from convulsion and

decrease pentylenetetrazole mortality in experimental animals.

The inhibitory effect of substituted-quinazolones of MAO activity of rat brain homogenate was recorded (Table 3). All the compounds produced inhibition of rat brain MAO at a final concentration of 1×10^{-8} M. The activity ranged from $25.6 \pm 0.3412\%$ to $70.8 \pm 0.4211\%$. Methyl group at position R and R₁ exhibited maximum degree of inhibition ($70.8 \pm 0.4181\%$), while chloro group at the position R₁ and bromo group at X reduced the activity. In general, electrophilic substituents at the position R and R₁ reduced the activity, and nucleophilic substituents at the same position reduced greater degree of enzymatic inhibition.

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